

**INFLUENCE OF FIBRE GEOMETRY ON THE PERFORMANCE
OF STEEL FIBRE REFRACTORY CONCRETE**

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ABSTRACT

Steel fibres are commonly used in the refractory industry to reinforce high temperature concretes. Little information is available on the effect of fibre geometry on refractory performance and in particular resistance to thermal shock. Eleven different melt extract fibre geometries were investigated, with fibre lengths of 10mm, 25mm and 50mm, and aspect ratios varying from 14 to 108. Beam specimens made from a proprietary dense hydraulically bonded castable, reinforced with 5% by weight of steel fibre, were cyclically heated and cooled on one face in a specially designed spalling furnace to condition them in a simulated service environment. Flexural tests were conducted at service and room temperatures to obtain flexural strengths and toughness indices. The relationships between fibre geometry (length, cross-section and aspect ratio) and both strength and toughness are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Stainless steel fibres have already proved very successful in the iron and steel, non-ferrous, petrochemical and rock products industries by prolonging the service life of refractory concretes (1, 2, 3). Melt extract, drawn wire and slit sheet steel fibre types have been used to reinforce cast, sprayed and moulded concretes. The melt extract fibre is currently best suited to the refractory market because of the range of alloy compositions available and its relatively low cost compared with those produced from wire or sheet materials.

There is still, however, very little published information available on the selection of the most appropriate steel alloy composition, fibre geometry and fibre content for specific applications (4, 5, 6). Suppliers and users of fibre reinforced refractories have found, within the relatively

short life span of these materials, that the 'standard' fibre sizes and grades are cost effective and little effort has been put into optimizing the composite's performance. The industry is also naturally secretive about information that it has obtained in the field.

The lack of test data can further be attributed to the absence of suitable standard test methods for fibre reinforced monolithic refractories. Even the standards for unreinforced refractory concrete are in many cases still related to those for refractory brick (7, 8). This problem has been addressed by Wooldridge and Easton (9) who proposed that specimens must be realistically conditioned before testing by cyclic heating and cooling on one face, to cause spalling by a fluctuating thermal gradient similar to that found in service. They tested their conditioned specimens in flexure at room temperature to obtain a modulus of rupture. Austin and Robins (10, 11) experimented further with cyclic conditioning and suggested that a toughness parameter was a more meaningful measure of refractory performance than flexural strength; they determined toughness indices from a room temperature flexure test, in addition to flexural strengths. Lankard (4) argued that flexure specimens should be tested at service temperature but did not condition specimens by cyclic heating.

The main aim of the present study is to investigate the influence of the geometry of AISI 310 grade stainless steel melt extract fibres on the performance of a proprietary 1300°C medium duty calcium aluminate bonded castable. The work also examines whether it is necessary to obtain flexural and toughness measurements at temperature in order to properly evaluate the performance of fibre reinforced refractories or whether it is possible to obtain meaningful results from a much simpler room temperature test.

MATERIALS

Refractory Concrete

A general duty dense refractory castable, 'Pinnacast 1400', was used throughout the test programme. This is a proprietary hydraulically bonded material containing 37% alumina with a maximum service temperature of 1400°C. The water content of each of the twelve mixes was approximately 14% by weight of dry material.

Steel Fibres

The investigation of the effects of varying fibre geometry was made possible by the manufacture of eleven different fibre sizes by Fibre Technology Ltd. This was achieved using 3 melt extraction wheels to produce fibre lengths of 10mm, 25mm and 50mm, and by machining the angle of the vee shaped edges to vary the kidney-shaped fibre cross-section.

The fibre length l_f , equivalent semi-circular diameter d_s , aspect ratio l_f/d_s and mean fibre weight m_f for each of the eleven fibre geometries is given in Table 1.

The equivalent semi-circular diameter was used as it had previously been found (10) to be the best approximation of the geometry of the kidney shape cross-section of the melt fibres. Values of d_s were obtained from specific gravity determinations on samples of each fibre type, where

$$d_s = \sqrt{\frac{8 \cdot m_f}{\pi \cdot l_f \cdot \rho_f}} \quad (1)$$

The average fibre density ρ_f of the AISI grade 310 (25% Cr, 20% Ni) stainless steel fibres was 7,890 kg/m³.

The fibre content of all the mixes was kept constant at 5% by weight of dry castable.

TABLE 1
Fibre geometry

Fibre type and mix no.	Fibre length l_f (mm)	Mean equivalent diameter d_s (mm)	Mean aspect ratio l_f/d_s	Mean fibre weight m_f (mg)
1	10	0.74	14	17
2	10	0.59	17	11
3	10	0.55	19	10
4	25	0.72	34	39
5	25	0.53	47	22
6	25	0.52	48	20
7	25	0.48	52	16
8	50	0.87	56	117
9	50	0.65	76	65
10	50	0.56	89	48
11	50	0.46	108	33

SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND CONDITIONING

Mixing, Casting and Curing

A total of one plain and eleven fibre reinforced mixes were prepared. Materials were mixed in a forced action concrete mixer and workability monitored by the ball-in-hand method described in ASTM C860-77 (12). Four 63.5mm x 63.5mm x 406mm beams were cast from each mix. The beams were cast in steel moulds and compacted on a vibrating table. Lifting handles were cast into the top surface of the beams to facilitate removal of the hot specimens from the spalling furnace into the insulated box prior to testing.

Specimens were placed under a plastic sheet membrane for 24 hours. After stripping, the specimens were oven dried at 110°C to constant weight.

Conditioning of Specimens

If tests are to give a useful measure of refractory performance the specimens must also be subjected to some form of simulated service conditions before destructive testing. Standard spalling tests for plain refractory concrete are unrealistic because of the uniform heating regime and the common use of a water quench as part of the heating/cooling cycle. In addition they generally specify the measurement of weight loss of small prisms which is unsuitable for fibre refractories because the fibres hold the cracked matrix material together.

The approach taken by the authors in this and a previous test programme (11) was to combine the need for simulated service conditioning of test specimens with the measurement of a toughness property of the steel fibre refractory concrete. The existing beam cycling furnace was modified to allow automated cyclic heating and cooling of four beam specimens to a pre-set heating and cooling regime prior to flexural and toughness testing.

Spalling Resistance Test Method

Beams were cyclically heated in the purpose built spalling furnace designed to be able to heat four 406mm x 63.5mm x 63.5mm beams on one face to temperatures up to 1600°C. This was achieved by stacking the beams vertically in a sliding door which would allow them to be moved aside for cooling, whilst a blanking piece prevented serious heat loss from the furnace (Figures 1 and 2).

The beams were placed in the spalling furnace and raised from 110°C to 1100°C over a 6 hour period and then soaked at this test temperature for 18

Figure 1. Beam spalling furnace, showing specimens in heating cycle position.

Figure 2. Beam spalling furnace, cooling cycle position.

hours. This firing rate is well within that specified in BS 1902 (7) of a maximum 300°C/hour heating rate and a 3 hour soak.

Immediately after the 18 hour soak, automated cycling of the beams between the spalling furnace and the cooling fan commenced. The four beams in the sliding door of the furnace were alternately heated at 1095°C for 40 minutes and then cooled by the fan for 20 minutes. All the beams were cycled 40 times.

TESTING OF SPECIMENS

At the end of the cycling period the specimens were held at the test temperature and subsequently removed one by one for testing at temperature. Each beam was placed in an insulated box designed to allow the hot specimen to be tested in flexure using centre-point loading. Specimens were tested with their hot face vertical over a span of 178mm in accordance with BS 1902 (7), ASTM C133-77 (8) and PRE recommendations R.21 (13) to determine their flexural strength and toughness. Tests were carried out using an Instron 6025 (100 kN capacity) screw driven testing machine operated under displacement control at a test speed of 0.25 mm/min; the total time for a flexural test being approximately 10 minutes.

A dummy test specimen was instrumented with thermocouples positioned at the hot face, middle, and cold face of the beam to determine the change in temperature profile during the test period in the insulated box, following transfer from the spalling furnace. Typically, whilst the hot face temperature reduced from 1200°C to 960°C and 870°C at 5 and 10 minutes, respectively, the mid-beam temperature reduced from 780°C to 700°C at 10 minutes.

The four specimens from each mix were first tested hot, and subsequently one half of each broken beam was tested at room temperature the following day. All flexural strength and toughness results quoted in the paper therefore represent an average of four test values.

FLEXURAL STRENGTH

The relationship between peak flexural strength and fibre aspect ratio is shown in Figure 3. Both hot and cold strengths increased with aspect ratio, the hot strengths being around 18% less than the cold. However, the improvement in flexural strength above an aspect ratio of around 60 is small. The strength/aspect ratio relationship does not appear to have been influenced by fibre length.

First-crack flexural strengths were also determined. The cold first-crack strength was not significantly affected by aspect ratio; this is in accordance with composite materials theory. It is of interest to note that a linear-elastic fracture mechanics approach would predict increasing strength with decreasing fibre spacing (i.e. increasing aspect ratio) at constant fibre volume. In contrast to the cold strength, the hot first-crack strength decreased slightly with increasing aspect ratio.

Figure 3. Influence of aspect ratio on peak flexural strength

TOUGHNESS

The authors have previously argued (11) that a toughness parameter is a more appropriate measure of spalling resistance than flexural strength. In this investigation two toughness indices ($I_{1,0}$, $I_{3,0}$) were calculated from the beam flexural load/deflection curve using a similar procedure to that described in ASTM C1018-85 (14). The $I_{1,0}$ and $I_{3,0}$ toughness values are plotted against aspect ratio in Figures 4 and 5.

In contrast with flexural strength, where as expected hot strength is below cold strength, the hot toughness values are greater than the cold ones. These higher toughness values may either be a result of the lower hot first-crack strength and modulus or of improved fibre/matrix bond at temperature. All beams failed by fibre pull-out rather than fibre breakage.

Both Figures 4 and 5 show toughness increasing with aspect ratio, the increases becoming smaller at higher aspect ratios. Again there is no discernible fibre length effect, all points lying around the same toughness/aspect ratio curve. It might be expected that a critical aspect ratio will eventually be reached, beyond which fibres begin to fracture and toughness index reduces. There is a suggestion in Figures 4 and 5 that this critical ratio may almost have been reached in the cold flexural tests.

Figure 4. Relationship between I_{10} toughness index and aspect ratio

Figure 5. Relationship between I_{30} toughness index and aspect ratio

The I_{30} toughness index is also plotted in Figure 6 against equivalent fibre diameter for the three fibre lengths. This gives another perspective on the influence of fibre geometry, toughness increasing with reducing fibre diameter (over the range investigated).

Figure 6. Influence of equivalent fibre diameter on toughness.

CONCLUSIONS

The construction of a simple insulating box allowed flexural tests to be carried out at temperature in a standard testing machine. Whilst testing hot is a better model of service conditions, testing at room temperature after cyclic conditioning is clearly easier. Cold testing overestimates flexural strength and underestimates toughness, but the relationships with aspect ratio are similar to those at temperature.

Flexural strength and toughness increased with aspect ratio at both test temperatures. For flexural strengthening, an aspect ratio of around 60 would appear to be a sensible choice. However, if improvements in toughness are taken to be a better indicator of refractory spalling resistance, the results suggest that a fibre aspect ratio of around 80 is more appropriate. Above these aspect ratios the improvements in performance are small and the likelihood of problems in mixing and placing increases.

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